

Tutorial for using **hydroMOPSO** to calibrate **SWAT+**

Study area: Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin, Chile

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1 Preface

The current availability of a large suite of computer hydrological models leads to consider different alternatives that offer different approaches, levels of complexity, and application goals (for reviews and discussions see, e.g., Clark et al. (2011); Devi et al. (2015); Peel and McMahon (2020); Guse et al. (2021); Horton et al. (2022)). Superimposing all the possibilities that these advances have given, the application of any model must guarantee an adequate predictive capacity, which leads hydrologists to concentrate their efforts on the calibration procedure, by which model results are adjusted to the measured ranges of certain observed variables (Refsgaard and Henriksen 2004).

To fit these models, for more than two decades it has been proposed to work on robust methods based on **multi-objective optimisation**, the first milestone being that developed by Yapo et al. (1998), who highlight the need to develop effective and efficient algorithms capable of exploiting all the useful information about the physical system contained in the time series of observed data used in the calibration.

Among the many nature-inspired families of heuristic algorithms, several multi-objective particle swarm optimisers (MOPSOs) have been developed in the last decades to find the Pareto-optimal front for multi-objective problems. However, there is a lack of software allowing the implementation of user-defined (hydrological/environmental) models, objective functions and model variables to be optimised.

This tutorial shows how to use the `hydroMOPSO > 0.2` multi-objective optimisation R package to calibrate an external hydrological model (SWAT+ in this case). If you already understand your SWAT+ configuration, the steps described here should help you prepare your own model for calibration.

2 Citation

This tutorial is based on the `hydroPSO` vignette, as well as several subsequent tutorials and scripts developed by Dr. Zambrano-Bigiarini and his team at the *Observatorio de Recursos Hídricos de La Araucanía Kimun-Ko* at *Universidad de La Frontera* (Chile).

If you find it useful, please cite it as Marinao-Rivas et al. (2025):

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3 Required hydroMOPSO version

This tutorial was developed for the new `hydroMOPSO >= 0.2-0`, released in October 2025, and accompanies the CRAN submission of version 0.2-0.

4 Objective

The main objective of this tutorial is to show how to use `hydroMOPSO` for finding **a set of solutions that satisfy Pareto optimality** in the multi-objective calibration of SWAT+, as opposed to providing a comprehensive explanation of hydrological concepts (e.g., calibration, verification, sensitivity analysis, uncertainty analysis) or an in-depth discussion of the hydrological results. Accordingly, all figures generated in this tutorial are not analysed in this document, leaving their examination to the discretion of the interested reader. All comments and questions are most welcome.

5 hydroMOPSO R package

`hydroMOPSO` is a multi-OS and model-independent package based on a multi-objective particle swarm optimiser designed to perform: *i*) model calibration and *ii*) an assessment of the calibration results.

With `hydroMOPSO` you can optimise:

- Any R function that returns one or more model outputs.
- Any R-based hydrological/environmental models (e.g., TUWmodel, GR4J, GR6J-CemaNeige).
- Any model that runs an executable file from the command line of any operative system (e.g., SWAT+, MODFLOW).

Key features:

- State-of-the-art multi-objective particle swarm optimiser (Lin et al. 2016).
- Several fine tuning options, with recommended default settings.
- Automated plotting of high quality graphics to support decision making.
- Multi-platform (GNU/Linux, macOS, Windows).
- Model-independent, i.e., it can be used to calibrate any model, whether an R function, and R-based or R-external model code.
- Parallel-capable, i.e., it can be easily run in multi-core machines or network clusters to reduce the computation time.
- Adherence to the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

5.1 hydroMOPSO in brief

hydroMOPSO is an R package that is built on the multi-objective NMPSO algorithm to provide an optimiser capable of preserving both convergence and diversity of the resulting Pareto-optimal front (Lin et al. 2016). During each iteration, the swarm keeps an external archive that ranks non-dominated particles through Balanceable Fitness Estimation, ensuring that elite solutions guide the search while maintaining a representative spread across the front.

The optimiser combines the canonical particle-swarm update with simulated binary crossover and polynomial mutation so that promising regions are refined without losing exploratory power. This hybrid search makes it possible to calibrate hydrological models that exhibit strongly contrasting objectives (e.g., low versus high flows) without heavy manual tuning.

The next subsection describes the NMPSO engine exposed by the package and highlights the control parameters that users can customise for their own applications.

5.2 The NMPSO engine

NMPSO is a novel particle swarm optimiser developed by (Lin et al. 2016), which was originally formulated to deal with many-objective optimisation problems (MaOPs; with more than two objectives). This algorithm combines a PSO approach with a evolutionary search mechanism (Lin et al. 2015) to maintain diversity and accelerate convergence to the Pareto-optimal front. A balanceable fitness estimation (BFE) procedure is used to rank particles in an repository or *external archive* (A), in order to provide an effective guidance to the true POF, while keeping diversity among particles.

Similar to the canonical PSO algorithm (Kennedy and Eberhart 1995), NMPSO starts with a random initialisation of the particles' positions within the parameter space. Considering a D -dimensional search space, the position for the i -th particle is represented by $\vec{X}_i = x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iD}$. The performance of each particle is evaluated through a problem-specific “*goodness-of-fit*” measure, which is the basis for updating \vec{X}_i . The personal/previous best, i.e. the best-known position of the i -th particle, is represented by $\vec{P}_i = p_{i1}, p_{i2}, \dots, p_{iD}$, whereas the global best, is represented by $\vec{G}_i = g_{i1}, g_{i2}, \dots, g_{iD}$. In NMPSO, the global best of each particle (\vec{G}_i) is randomly selected from the 10% particles with better BFE values in the external archive (Lin et al. 2016).

For the PSO search, NMPSO integrates a new formulation for velocity update equation (Lin et al. 2015), as follows:

$$\vec{V}_i^{(t+1)} = \omega \vec{V}_i^t + c_1 \vec{U}_1^t \otimes (\vec{P}_i^t - \vec{X}_i^t) + c_2 \vec{U}_2^t \otimes (\vec{G}^t - \vec{X}_i^t) + c_3 \vec{U}_3^t \otimes (\vec{G}^t - \vec{P}_i^t) \quad (1)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, with N equal to swarm size; and $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, with T equal to the maximum number of iterations. ω is the inertia weight, c_1 and c_2 are the cognitive and social acceleration coefficients, and \vec{U}_1 and \vec{U}_2 are independent and uniformly distributed random vectors in $[0, 1]$ (note that \otimes denotes element-wise vector multiplication). c_3 and \vec{U}_3 are the coefficient and uniformly distributed random vector, respectively, for the last term in the velocity equation. This last term has been reported to contribute to finding a better POF for MaOPs (Lin et al. 2016). However, in preliminary tests, for MOPs (up to three objective functions) it introduces an important burden in terms of the number of model evaluations required to achieve the POF. Therefore, in the tests carried out in this work, this term has not been considered.

After the PSO search, the non-dominated particles in the swarm are added to A to keep track of the POF along the iterations. When the size of the updated repository is larger then the maximum size of the external archive

(N_e) the BFE method is used to select non-dominated solutions to be kept in A , which are considered to be good representatives of the entire POF.

Afterwards, NMPSO performs evolutionary operations on non-dominated solutions in A , to allow beneficial exchange of information among its particles. In particular, the simulated binary crossover (SBX) operator is used to allow the interchange of useful gene segments, and polynomial-based mutation (PM) is carried out to add a small disturbance to improve local search. Therefore, if the size of the current external archive is N_A , with $N_A \leq N_e$, the two previous evolutionary operations impose a number N_A of additional evaluations for each iteration. More details on BFE and the two genetic operations can be found in (Lin et al. 2016) and (Lin et al. 2015), respectively.

5.3 Requirements for a model-independent calibration

For the calibration of models external to R, specifications are required on how changes to model parameter values will be made via two standard input files, in addition to the wrapper function that will be used to read

5.4 SWAT+ parameters

SWAT+ has an huge number of parameters that can be considered in the calibration, and the user has some freedom to choose which of them will be modified. However, unless there is a vast knowledge of the model, we recommend the following guidelines:

- The work of Bieger et al. (2017) (in which the restructuring of SWAT into SWAT+ was presented) and subsequent works that have dealt with the model.
- The SWAT+ IO Documentation and the SWAT+ Editor documentation, both available at <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/user/io>.
- Details described in the SWATPlusEditor IDE, which are compatible with the model documentation.
- Parameter descriptions placed in the source code of the model available in <https://bitbucket.org/swatplus/swatplus.editor/src/master/>¹.

We chose ten parameters for this tutorial, applying them as replacement rules on the native SWAT+ input files; these are controlled through the `calibration.cal` file, which in turn supports direct (`absval`), multiplicative (`abschg`) and additive (`pctchg`) adjustments. According to the *SWAT+ Input/Output Documentation* (SWAT+ Development Team 2023), each parameter affects the following fields:

- `perco` (`hydrology.hyd`): percolation coefficient that regulates vertical water flux from the soil profile into the shallow aquifer.
- `latq_co` (`hydrology.hyd`): linear factor for lateral soil flow that controls the subsurface runoff response across HRUs.
- `alpha` → `alpha_bf` (`aquifer.aqu`): baseflow alpha factor governing how quickly the shallow aquifer contributes discharge to the channels.
- `cn2` (`cntable.lum`): SCS curve number II that determines the rainfall-runoff partition for each soil/land-use combination.
- `awc` (`soils.sol`): available water capacity per layer; in `calibration.cal` the settings `soil_lyr1 = 1` and `soil_lyr2 = 6` apply the change to the full soil profile.
- `k` (`soils.sol`): saturated hydraulic conductivity (`k`), modulating percolation and subsurface drainage.
- `flo_min` (`aquifer.aqu`): minimum shallow-aquifer storage required to allow return flow (`flo_min`).
- `revap_min` (`aquifer.aqu`): water-depth threshold in the aquifer that triggers the revaporation process (`revap_min`).
- `revap_co` (`aquifer.aqu`): revaporation coefficient (`revap`) controlling the fraction of water moving upward from the aquifer.
- `deep_seep` (`aquifer.aqu`): fraction of recharge percolating to the deep aquifer (`rchg_dp`), used by SWAT+ to balance groundwater losses.

6 Installation

Installing the latest stable version of `hydroMOPSO`.

¹We also encourage more motivated users to dive into the model and get in touch with the SWAT+ community via the SWAT+model group.

```
install.packages("hydroMOPSO")
```

Alternatively, you can also try the under-development version of `hydroMOPSO` (from Gitlab):

```
if (!require(devtools)) install.packages("devtools")
library(devtools)
install_gitlab("rmarinao/hydroMOPSO")
```

Installing the latest stable version of `hydroTSM` and `hydroGOF`. These packages will be used to evaluate the performance of the simulated streamflow.

```
install.packages("hydroTSM")
install.packages("hydroGOF")
```

7 SWAT+ model set up

All `SWAT+` projects bundled with this tutorial include the full `TxtInOut` directory required to run the model on GNU/Linux, macOS, or Windows. Before launching the calibration, verify that the executable for your platform is available and that the auxiliary files discussed in Section [@ref\(paramfiles\)](#) are consistent with your local copy of the project. Keeping those files synchronised avoids silent failures when `hydroMOPSO` edits the inputs prior to each simulation.

8 SWAT+

8.1 SWAT+ in brief

`SWAT+` is an open-source, semi-distributed hydrological model that simulates water quantity and quality for both surface and groundwater domains, supporting analyses of management practices, land use, and climate change impacts (Bieger et al. 2017). It succeeds the original Soil and Water Assessment Tool (`SWAT`; Arnold et al. (1998)), whose decades-long application history covers a wide range of climates, management strategies, and pollutant transport studies (Douglas-Mankin et al. 2010; Gassman et al. 2007).

The redesign introduced in `SWAT+` focuses on modularity: hydrological response units, channels, reservoirs, and management operations can now be connected through explicit spatial objects and processes. This flexibility facilitates the representation of complex catchments but also increases the number of parameters that may require calibration. Coupling `SWAT+` with `hydroMOPSO` addresses that challenge by automating parameter exploration while respecting the model's file-based workflow.

The following subsections describe the study area, model inputs, and configuration adopted for this tutorial, which you can adapt to your own watershed once the base project is properly assembled.

8.2 Study area

The area of study considered in this tutorial corresponds to the *Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin* (Figure 1, Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin onwards), located in *La Araucanía* Region in Chile. The delimitation of this catchment is defined from the *Trancura antes de Llafenco* fluvioimetric station (code 9414001), and its entire effluent is a tributary of the *Río Toltén* basin.

From the `CR2MET v2.5` hydro-meteorological gridded data (Boisier et al. 2018), for the period 1980-2020, the monthly climatology in this catchment (panels c and d in Figure 1) shows rainfall throughout the year, reaching the maximum amounts between May and August with values ranging between 380 and 480 mm/month. The average temperature ranges between 3 °C (winter) and 14 °C (summer). According to the data from the outlet gauging station, the mean annual flow is 106.8 m³/s.

8.3 Model set up

The hydrological model in `SWAT+` was developed according to the guidelines set out in the manual `QSWAT+Manual` and `SWATPlusEditor`.

Figure 1: Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin.

Although this tutorial is not focused on the development of the model, it is important that we point out the following considerations and characteristics of the model developed particularly for this example.

8.3.1 Input data

- Precipitation and maximum/minimum air temperature data: This meteorological forcings were taken from the CR2met gridded product (Boisier et al. 2018), which covers the entire continental Chilean territory, at a spatial resolution of 0.05° and at a daily scale.
- Digital elevation model (DEM): The DEM used for the watershed delineation is a union of data from TanDEM-X ©DLR 2017 and the ALOS PALSAR product (Rosenqvist et al. 2007), resulting in a gridded product of 12.5 m resolution.
- Land use: This data was taken from a land cover product currently under development in the PCI NSFC 190018 project in which this work is framed.
- Soil: Information on soil types was discretised on the basis of textural classes derived from a SoilGrids-based product currently under development in the framework of the FONDAP-ANID 1522A0001 project, which has a downscaling and an adjustment with ground observations for the Chilean territory. For SoilGrids250m itself see the work of Hengl et al. (2017).
- Daily streamflow: Daily time serie was taken from observations recorded by the General Water Bureau of Chile, which are available on the website *Estadísticas estaciones DGA*.

8.3.2 SWAT+ project characteristics

With the above information, a model for the Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin was developed with the following final characteristics:

- Area: $1,417.9 \text{ km}^2$ (141,788 ha)
- Simulation period configured in SWAT+: 1999–2005
- Subbasins: 23
- HRUs: 307
- Channels: 44

- Aquifers: 47
- Routing units / Landscape units: 88 / 88
- Recall objects (point sources/inlets): 148
- Reservoirs, export coefficients and delivery ratio: not represented (0)
- Predominant land uses: temperate evergreen forest (`frse_tems`, ~72%), shrubland (`shrb`, ~11%), bare soil (`bsvg`, ~7%), grassland (`gras`, ~5%), cropland (`crdy`) and forest plantations (`euca`) in smaller proportions (<3%), with isolated wetlands (`wetw`).
- Predominant soil type: Sandy Loam (SL), hydrological group B (Total depth: 2 m)
- Slope bands: not considered

One last piece of information that will be required later is that the channel number for the outlet on this particular model is set to 68, i.e., `channel_id=68`.

8.3.3 Material for this tutorial

8.3.4 TxtInOut directory to be used in this vignette

The previously detailed model is bundled with this vignette as the `TxtInOut` directory and is ready to run on GNU/Linux, macOS and Windows (each platform has its corresponding `SWAT+` executable). In future revisions we expect to provide the final archive through the DOI of the associated Zenodo release, so that readers can cite and download the exact version used here.

9 hydroMOPSO set up

9.1 Loading required packages

We will start by loading the minimum packages required for calibration. If you do not have them in your current R environment you can download them from CRAN. The `hydroTSM` (Zambrano-Bigiarini 2020b) and `hydroGOF` (Zambrano-Bigiarini 2020a) packages are used here to manipulate the hydrological time series and to compute goodness-of-fit functions, respectively.

```
# Time-series handling, goodness-of-fit metrics, and optimisation
library(hydroTSM)
library(hydroGOF)
library(hydroMOPSO)
```

9.2 General settings

We now proceed to delineate general specifications for directories and variables. This involves defining a set of variables that will eventually be integrated into the algorithmic specifications.

9.2.1 Main directory

The classic `TxtInOut` folder itself, where both the inputs and outputs of the `SWAT+` model are hosted, shall be used as the parent directory. Do not forget to leave the model executable in this folder (e.g., `rev60.5.4_64rel.exe` for Windows users).

```
model_directory <- "/path/to/your/TxtInOut" # modify with your own path
setwd(model_directory)
```

Of course, you must change the string `model_directory` to the current path of your `TxtInOut` folder.

9.2.2 NMPSO minimal specifications

Before starting the calibration, it is critical to outline a few key specifications. The most important are the number of particles that conduct the PSO search (N , stored as `n_part`), the maximum number of particles retained in the external archive (N_e , stored as `max_rep`), and the maximum number of particles that undergo genetic operations inside that archive (max_{GO} , stored as `max_cross`), in line with the NMPSO algorithm. A study by Marinao-Rivas and Zambrano-Bigiarini (2021) tested sixteen different combinations of N , N_e , and max_{GO} and recommended the configuration $N = 10$, $N_e = 100$, and $max_{GO} = 0.5N_e$ to maximise effectiveness and efficiency.

```
n_part    <- 10L  # number of particles that execute the PSO search
max_rep   <- 100L # maximum number of particles positioned in the external archive
max_cross <- 50L  # maximum number of particles performing genetic operations in the external archive
max_it    <- 100L # maximum number of iterations
max_eval  <- 1000000L
```

9.2.3 Parallelisation (optional)

Parallelisation of runs may be very necessary if the model in question is highly complex and leads to a long execution time. In these cases you could make good use of your computational resources and make the calibration take less time than it would take if all executions were done one after the other (serial). When parallel execution is desired use `parallel_mode <- "parallel"` on GNU/Linux and macOS, or `parallel_mode <- "parallelWin"` on Windows.)

```
parallel_mode <- ifelse(
  tolower(Sys.info()[["sysname"]]) == "windows", "parallelWin", "parallel"
)
```

In our experience, on a desktop computer with 8 cores and about 16 GB of RAM you could comfortably use 6 nodes (`par.nnodes` en `hydroMOPSO`, configurado aquí mediante `par.nnodes`) busy running the model while you can still make use of the machine. Also consider that for each node we have to load the libraries that we have indicated above, so we will store them as strings in the variable `par_pkgs`.

If you do not wish to parallelise simply indicate `parallel_mode <- "none"`.

```
par.nnodes <- 6L
par_pkgs    <- c("hydroGOF", "hydroTSM", "hydroMOPSO")
```

If you can connect to large multi-core machines or network clusters note that for the number of nodes, at the most you can specify `max(n_part, max_cross)`. This is by no means a limitation of the algorithm, it is simply because the maximum between `npart` y `maxcross` (los nombres esperados por `hydroMOPSO`) is the maximum number of runs for each step of the algorithm.

9.2.4 Auxiliary function

Unlike R-based models, where we can directly access the outputs within the R environment, in external models such as `SWAT+` we need to read the outputs that are written to text files in the `TxtInOut` folder. For this we have prepared a script with the necessary function (`swat2zoo()`) to read the `SWAT+` outputs needed for this tutorial, specifically daily streamflows. `swat2zoo()` it has been formulated to be as flexible as possible so that any other output contained in some `.txt` file could be read. In Appendix A you can find the function, which by the way is already included in the material of this tutorial. In the following lines we simply show how to load it into the current R environment:

```
source("functions/read_out_swatplus.R")
```

9.2.5 Problem specifications (just strings)

It is also necessary to define some strings that will be used later for plots and tables, specifically a main title, the names of the objective functions, the name of the output variable(s) and their units of measure.

```
main_char      <- c("Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin")
objs_names_char <- c("KGE_Q", "KGE_lf_Q")
obs_names_char <- c("Streamflow")
obs_units_char <- c("m3/s")
```

9.3 Time window for calibration

Now we will define the vectors used to configure the simulation period: a one-year warm-up (full 1999) and a calibration window covering 2000-2005. This warm-up period can be extended if data availability allows.

```
### Calibration period
warmup_dates <- hydroTSM::dip("1999-01-01", "1999-12-31")
cal_dates    <- hydroTSM::dip("2000-01-01", "2005-12-31")
full_dates   <- c(warmup_dates, cal_dates)
```

The `time.sim` file stores the start and end years used during simulation. Keep its entries (row 3, columns 15–18 and 35–38) aligned with the warm-up and calibration dates set below so that SWAT+ remains synchronised with the R settings.

```
start_full <- full_dates[1]
end_full   <- full_dates[length(full_dates)]

yrc_start <- as.numeric(format(start_full, "%Y"))
yrc_end   <- as.numeric(format(end_full, "%Y"))
```

9.4 Observed data

The daily streamflows (Q [m^3/s]) to be used in the calibration are attached in the material of this tutorial, these data was obtained from the online information web-site of the Chilean Water Bureau (DGA).

```
ts_qobs      <- zoo::read.csv.zoo("Obs/Qobs_Trancura_Llafenco.csv", format = "%Y-%m-%d")
ts_qobs_full <- window(ts_qobs, start = start_full, end = end_full)

list_obs_cal <- list(ts_qobs_full)
```

9.5 SWAT+ parameters to be calibrated

At this point it is necessary to specify the `Paramfiles.txt` and `ParamRanges.txt` files, presented above in generic form. Both files should be placed in a folder conveniently called `MOPSO.in` inside the parent folder `TxtInOut`. Of course, these ready-made files are attached to the material associated with this tutorial and the following table shows the selected parameters in summary form.

Table: SWAT+ parameters considered for calibration. The **Change** column mirrors the `TypeChange` directive passed to hydroMOPSO; in this tutorial the optimiser always writes replacements (`repl`) because the true transformation is governed by `calibration.cal`.

`calibration.cal` stores the native SWAT+ change rules (`absval`, `abschg`, `pctchg`). Because we adopt that internal convention, every parameter listed below is still triggered as a replacement (`repl`) on the hydroMOPSO side.

ID	Short description	Units	Archive	Change	Range
awc	Available water capacity	% change	soils.sol	repl	10 - 300
k	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	% change	soils.sol	repl	10 - 200
latq_co	Lateral soil flow coefficient (linear)	-	hydrology.hyd	repl	0.75 - 0.92
perco	Percolation coefficient	-	hydrology.hyd	repl	0 - 1
revap_min	Threshold depth of water for revap to occur	m	aquifer.aqu	repl	1 - 10
flo_min	Minimum aquifer storage to allow return flow	m	aquifer.aqu	repl	1 - 10
alpha	Baseflow alpha factor	1/day	aquifer.aqu	repl	0 - 0.015
revap_co	Groundwater revap coefficient	-	aquifer.aqu	repl	0.02 - 0.2
deep_seep	Deep aquifer percolation fraction	-	aquifer.aqu	repl	0.0 - 0.1

As mentioned, making these files is the hardest part of the whole job as identifying each parameter and seeing the exact position where it is located in one of the `TxtInOut` files can be a bit challenging. However, if you are well familiar with the model and considering that you can facilitate your work with different tools the task can be eased a bit (in time). We strongly recommend the use of the text editor `Sublime Text` which has several tools that can make the work easier.

9.5.1 ParamFiles.txt and ParamRanges.txt files

These two files provide the main bridge between `hydroMOPSO` and `SWAT+`, specifying both the search ranges considered during calibration (`ParamRanges.txt`) and the location of the parameters inside the model inputs (`ParamFiles.txt`). In each iteration, `hydroMOPSO` edits the native `SWAT+` files according to these instructions and then launches a new simulation.

`SWAT+` projects usually expose a `TxtInOut` directory that stores files such as `hydrology.hyd`, `soils.sol`, and `aquifer.aqu`. If you normally work via graphical interfaces like `SWATPlusEditor`, take the time to inspect these text files with an editor (`Visual Studio Code`, `Sublime Text` or `Notepad++`), because column positions and numeric formatting matter.

Both configuration files can be built from scratch as long as their structure is respected. The first table below summarises the template required by `ParamFiles.txt`. Note that a single parameter can span multiple rows if it appears across different files.

ParameterNmb	ParameterName	Filename	Row.Number	Col.Start	Col.End	DecimalPlaces	RefValue
1	par_1	file_1	row_1	cstart_1	cend_1	dec_1	ref_1
2	par_1	file_2	row_2	cstart_2	cend_2	dec_2	ref_2
...
n	par_n	file_m	row_m	cstart_m	cend_m	dec_m	ref_m

ParameterNmbr	ParameterName	Filename	Row.Number	Col.Start	Col.End	DecimalPlaces	RefValue
1	perco	calibration.cal	4	35	44	5	0
2	latq_co	calibration.cal	5	35	44	5	0
3	alpha	calibration.cal	6	35	44	5	0
4	cn2	calibration.cal	7	35	44	5	0
5	awc	calibration.cal	8	35	44	5	0
6	k	calibration.cal	9	35	44	5	0
7	flo_min	calibration.cal	10	35	44	5	0
8	revap_min	calibration.cal	11	35	44	5	0
9	revap_co	calibration.cal	12	35	44	5	0
10	deep_seep	calibration.cal	13	35	44	5	0

Keep the header exactly as shown, set `RefValue = 0` for replacement (`repl`) changes, and double-check the column spans (`Col.Start`, `Col.End`) so that the number of digits and decimals always fit. The same parameter often requires multiple rows across different files, so plan for this when preparing the template. We also recommend sticking with plain spaces as column separators instead of tabs, because they are easier to inspect in monospaced editors.

The second file, `ParamRanges.txt`, states the admissible search bounds and the type of change to be applied during calibration. For multiplicative (`mult`) or additive (`addi`) cases, the `Min4Change` and `Max4Change` columns record the absolute limits around the reference value.

ParameterNmbr	ParameterName	MinValue	MaxValue	TypeChange	Min4Change	Max4Change
1	par_1	minval_1	maxval_1	typ_1	min_1	max_1
2	par_2	minval_2	maxval_2	typ_2	min_2	max_2
3	par_3	minval_3	maxval_3	typ_3	min_3	max_3

ParameterNmbr	ParameterName	MinValue	MaxValue	TypeChange	Min4Change	Max4Change
4	par_4	minval_4	maxval_4	typ_4	min_4	max_4
...
n	par_n	minval_n	maxval_n	typ_n	min_n	max_n

ParameterNmbr	ParameterName	MinValue	MaxValue	TypeChange	Min4Change	Max4Change
1	perco	0	1	repl	0	0
2	latq_co	0.75	0.92	repl	0	0
3	alpha	0	0.015	repl	0	0
4	cn2	-20	20	repl	0	0
5	awc	10	300	repl	0	0
6	k	10	200	repl	0	0
7	flo_min	1	10	repl	0	0
8	revap_min	1	10	repl	0	0
9	revap_co	0.02	0.2	repl	0	0
10	deep_seep	0	0.1	repl	0	0

Preparing these two files is often the most time-consuming step. Invest time in validating the positions, since typos or misaligned columns usually translate into silent but biased simulations.

9.6 Objectives functions

Before moving on to multi-site or multi-variable calibration, in this tutorial we have chosen to work with a simpler case: multi-objective calibration with two goodness-of-fit metrics applied to the same variable (streamflows).

9.6.1 Objective 1: adjustment of medium-high daily flows

For this we chose Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE):

$$KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + (\alpha - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2}$$

where $r = r_{Pearson}$ = Pearson correlation coefficient between observed and simulated values; $\alpha = \sigma_{sim}/\sigma_{obs}$, the ratio between the average of simulated and observed values; and $\beta = \mu_{sim}/\mu_{obs}$, ratio between the standard deviation of simulated and observed values.

9.6.2 Objective 2: adjustment of low flows

For this objective we use the low-flow Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE_{lf}) proposed by Garcia et al. (2017), available in the `hydroGOF` package (`KGE1f`).

9.7 Wrapper R function to interface SWAT+ with hydroMOPSO

For the calibration of SWAT+ (or any other hydrological model), you must build an R function that provides the outputs used by `hydroMOPSO` to move forward in the parameter space throughout the iterations.

9.7.1 Some considerations

Before doing so, it is important to take into account some aspects that will be detailed below:

- GNU/Linux users can execute `./rev60.5.7_64rel_linux` directly; no environment variables require adjustment, so the bash launcher is merely a convenience wrapper on this platform.
- macOS (Apple Silicon M1/M2) users should rely on the `rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh` launcher. The script exports `DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.` before invoking `rev60.5.7_64rel_mac` so that the packaged `libomp5.dylib` (Intel OpenMP runtime) stored alongside the executable is found at runtime.

- Windows users must call the bundled executable `rev60.5.7_64rel_win.exe`, ensuring it resides inside the `TxtInOut` folder.
- The function `swat2zoo()` previously stated as the function needed to read the SWAT+ outputs will be required at this point.

`libiomp5.dylib` is the Intel OpenMP runtime that accompanies the SWAT+ macOS build. Because the executables were compiled with Intel Fortran/oneAPI, the library is needed at run time to manage the multi-threaded (OpenMP) sections of the code. macOS does not ship this runtime by default, so bundling the `.dylib` inside `TxtInOut` keeps the distribution self-contained; exporting `DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.` tells the dynamic loader to look in that folder.

- Since we will only use streamflows as output variables, we will have to read only one output file from SWAT+, in this case `channel_sd_day.txt`. The name of the column in which the streamflows are placed in this file is `flo_out`.
- As mentioned about this particular model, to identify the outlet within this file it is necessary to locate channel 68, i.e., `channel_id=68`.

9.7.2 Wrapper R function to run the model

Adapt the `exe.fname` argument to your platform: keep `"/rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh"` on GNU/Linux and macOS, but switch to `"/rev60.5.7_64rel_win.exe"` on Windows.

For all the wrapper functions to be used with `hydroMOPSO`, the following requirements **MUST** be taken into account:

1) Mandatory inputs: Eight input arguments must be identical to those presented below, both in class and name:

- 1.1) `param.values`: class 'numeric'. Vector with parameter set of the model. Default NOT required.
- 1.2) `obs`: class 'list'. List with time series of observations of the output variables. Default required.
- 1.3) `objs.names`: class 'character'. Vector with the names of the optimisation objectives. Default required.
- 1.4) `var.names`: class 'character'. Vector with the names of the output variables. Default required.
- 1.5) `var.units`: class 'character'. Vector with the units of measurement of the output variables. Default required.
- 1.6) `full.period`: class 'Date'. Vector with the dates of the full period (warmup + calibration). Default required.
- 1.7) `warmup.period`: class 'Date'. Vector with the dates of the warmup period. Default required.
- 1.8) `cal.period`: class 'Date'. Vector with the dates of the calibration period. Default required.

Other input arguments will be needed depending on how the hydrological model is handled, and all of these require default values.

2) Mandatory outputs: The function must return a `list` called `out`, with two elements that must be identical to those presented below, both in class and name:

- 2.1) `objs`: class `numeric`. Vector with as many elements as objectives included in the calibration.
- 2.2) `sim`: class `zoo`. Matrix/vector with the time series of the output variables considered in the calibration. If there is only one variable involved, it can be a vector with as many elements as there are dates in the time series; and if there are more variables, then there will be as many columns as variables and as many rows as dates in the time series.

An example of such a function for calibrating SWAT+ with `hydroMOPSO` is the following:

```
swat_hydromod_cal <- function(param.values,
                              Obs = list_obs_cal,
                              Objs.names = objs_names_char,
                              var.names = obs_names_char,
                              var.units = obs_units_char,
                              full.period = full_dates,
                              warmup.period = warmup_dates,
                              cal.period = cal_dates,
```

```

        model.drty = getwd(), ...){

if (is.na(model.drty))
  model.drty <- getwd()

exe_fname <- ifelse(tolower(Sys.info()[["sysname"]]) == "windows",
  "rev60.5.7_64rel_win.exe",
  "./rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh"
)

sims <- hydromod(
  param.values = param.values,
  model.drty   = model.drty,
  param.files  = "MOPSO.in/ParamFiles.txt",
  param.ranges = "MOPSO.in/ParamRanges.txt",
  exe.fname    = exe_fname,
  exe.args     = "",
  verbose      = FALSE,
  stderr       = FALSE,
  stdout       = FALSE,
  out.FUNs     = c("swat2zoo", "swat2zoo"),
  out.FUNs.args = list(
    list(
      file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt", id = 68, name.col = "flo_out",
      first.date = full.period[1], last.date = full.period[length(full.period)]
    ),
    list(
      file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt", id = 68, name.col = "flo_out",
      first.date = full.period[1], last.date = full.period[length(full.period)]
    )
  )
) # 'out.FUNs.args'
) # 'hydromod'

qsim_model <- sims[[1]]
qsim       <- qsim_model
qobs       <- Obs[[1]]

na_index <- rep(FALSE, length(full.period))
na_index[full.period %in% warmup.period] <- TRUE

qsim[na_index] <- NA
qobs[na_index] <- NA

if (sum(na_index) == sum(is.na(qsim))) {
  gof1 <- hydroGOF::KGE(sim = qsim, obs = qobs, method = "2009")
  gof2 <- hydroGOF::KGE1f(sim = qsim, obs = qobs, method = "2009")
} else {
  gof1 <- NA
  gof2 <- NA
} # ELSE end

out          <- vector("list", 2)
out[[1]]    <- c(gof1, gof2)
names(out[[1]]) <- Objs.names

out[[2]] <- list(qsim_model)

names(out) <- c("Objs", "sim")

```

```

return(out)
} # 'swat_hydromod_cal' end

```

9.8 Testing the calibration wrapper function

With the wrapper function created, the next step is to verify that it works correctly using default parameters, checking at least:

- That the model could be executed using the function.
- That the model is simulating finite values of the output variable, and therefore deriving finite values of the objective functions.
- That the model, although with default parameters, is simulating values of the same order of magnitude as the corresponding observed variable.
- That the calibration and warm-up periods coincide with those previously entered.

Considering the high probability of errors in the preparation of the wrapper function, we strongly emphasise that the modeller, through this test, is satisfied with the previously indicated points.

Thus, we suggest starting by specifying default values for the parameters to be calibrated and then running the wrapper function, storing the outputs in an object such as `default_results_cal`:

```

paramfile      <- read.table("MOPSO.in/ParamRanges.txt", header = TRUE)
lower          <- paramfile[["MinValue"]]
upper         <- paramfile[["MaxValue"]]
default_param  <- (upper + lower) / 2
names(default_param) <- paramfile[["ParameterName"]]

default_results_cal <- swat_hydromod_cal(param.values = default_param)
default_sim_cal    <- default_results_cal[["sim"]]
default_objs_cal  <- default_results_cal[["Objs"]]

```

To make the verification of the wrapper function visual, we prepare a function called `SimVsObs`, which is executed as follows:

```

SimVsObs(
  sim           = default_sim_cal,
  obs          = list_obs_cal,
  obj.values   = default_objs_cal,
  obj.names    = objs_names_char,
  var.names    = obs_names_char,
  var.units    = obs_units_char,
  legend.sim   = "Simulated",
  legend.obs   = "Observed",
  full.period  = full_dates,
  warmup.period = warmup_dates,
  cal.period   = cal_dates,
  main         = "Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin (SWAT+ not calibrated yet)",
  analysis.period = "calibration",
  digits.round = 4
)

```

In this case everything is working correctly, so you can go to the calibration.

9.9 Running the calibration

Other input arguments, such as the type of problem (max/min), the type of initialisation, the maximum number of model evaluations, and the maximum number of iterations, may be overridden by modellers. All these arguments are detailed in the package documentation.

Figure 2: Visual verification of the operation of the wrapper function.

When the user replicates this example, we suggest changing the `plot = FALSE` argument to `plot = TRUE`, since in this way he will be able to visualise the evolution of the Pareto front throughout the iterations. In this tutorial, this option was deactivated only due to the limitations that means to write a document.

hydroMOPSO starts with a random initialisation. To make the results replicable, it is necessary to indicate a specific random seed so that the results are replicable (random seed).

```
set.seed(200) # random seed for reproducibility
```

```
model_fun_args <- list(
  Obs           = list_obs_cal,
  Objs.names    = objs_names_char,
  var.names     = obs_names_char,
  var.units     = obs_units_char,
  full.period   = full_dates,
  warmup.period = warmup_dates,
  cal.period    = cal_dates,
  model.drty    = getwd()
)
```

```
cal_results <- hydroMOPSO(
  fn = "hydromod",
  control = list(
    MinMax      = "max",
    Xini.type   = "lhs",
    write2disk  = TRUE,
    parallel    = parallel_mode,
    par.nnodes  = par_nnodes,
    par.pkgs    = par_pkgs,
    npart       = n_part,
    maxrep      = max_rep,
    maxcross    = max_cross,
    maxit       = max_it,
    maxeval     = max_eval,
    verbose     = TRUE,
    REPORT      = 1,
    digits      = 8,
    digits.dom  = 4
  ),
  model.FUN = "swat_hydromod_cal",
  model.FUN.args = model_fun_args,
```

```
obj.thr      = list(c(-0.41, 1), c(-0.41, 1)),  
BC.space.norm = TRUE  
)
```

After the run finishes, you can plot the results stored on disk with:

```
plot_results()
```


Figure 3: Final Pareto optimal front obtained during calibration.

Figure 4: Parameter distributions across the Pareto-optimal front.

Figure 5: Dotty plots for Pareto solutions ordered by objective 1.

Figure 6: Dotty plots for Pareto solutions ordered by objective 2.

Figure 7: Hydrograph bands generated from Pareto-optimal solutions.

Figure 8: Best-compromise hydrograph compared with observations.

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11 Appendix A: swat2zoo() function

Function to read SWAT+ outputs (.txt files). It has been formulated to be as flexible as possible, and at least up to SWATplus_rev60.5.4 it is able to adequately read streamflow (channel_sd_morph_day.txt), evapotranspiration and soil moisture outputs at basin scale (basin_wb_day.txt).

```
swat2zoo <- function(file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt", id,
                    first.date = NULL, last.date = NULL, name.col){

  library(zoo)

  head <- as.character(read.table(file.name, skip = 1, nrows = 1, sep = ""))

  indexVar <- which(head == name.col)
  indexID <- which(head == "gis_id")

  classes <- rep("NULL", length(head))
  classes[indexID] <- "character"
  classes[indexVar] <- "numeric"

  df.read <- read.table(file.name, skip = 3, colClasses = classes, sep = "")

  all.id.out <- as.character(df.read[, 1])
  all.out <- as.numeric(df.read[, 2])

  index.id <- all.id.out %in% id
  main.out <- all.out[index.id]

  indexDates <- c(2, 3, 4)

  classesDates <- rep("NULL", length(head))
  classesDates[indexDates] <- "numeric"

  df.fecha <- read.table(file.name, skip = 3, colClasses = classesDates, sep = "")[index.id, ]

  fechas <- as.Date(apply(df.fecha, FUN = paste, collapse = "-", MARGIN = 1), format = "%m-%d-%Y")

  out.zoo <- zoo(main.out, fechas)

  if (!is.null(first.date) & !is.null(last.date)) {
    out.zoo <- window(out.zoo, start = first.date, end = last.date)
  }

  return(out.zoo)
}
```

12 Appendix B: calibration.cal reference

The `calibration.cal` file bundled with this tutorial is located at `TxtInOut/calibration.cal`. It contains ten parameter rules chosen for this example and applied by SWAT+ during calibration; users are free to redefine them to suit their own projects.

```
calibration.cal: written by SWAT+ editor v2.3.1 on 2025-09-28 19:47 for SWAT+ rev.60.5.7
10
cal_parm      chg_typ      chg_val      conds  soil_lyr1  soil_lyr2    yr1      yr2      day1      day2  obj_tot
perco         absval       0.50000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
latq_co       absval       0.83500     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
alpha         absval       0.00750     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
cn2           abschg       0.00000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
awc           pctchg      155.00000   0      1          6            0        0        0        0    0
k             pctchg      105.00000   0      1          6            0        0        0        0    0
flo_min       absval       5.50000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
revap_min     absval       5.50000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
revap_co      absval       0.11000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
deep_seep     absval       0.05000     0      0          0            0        0        0        0    0
```

The user should be aware that there are two views for parameter change types: those native to SWAT+ and those of hydroMOPSO.

The model file `calibration.cal` uses the native SWAT+ change types:

- **absval**: the number becomes the new absolute parameter value.
- **abschg**: the number is treated as an additive delta that SWAT+ applies internally to the baseline value.
- **pctchg**: the number denotes a percentage change (100 keeps the baseline, 150 means +50%, etc.), not a literal multiplier.

On the hydroMOPSO side, the `TypeChange` column in `ParamRanges.txt` carries its own set of rules (replacement, additive change, multiplicative change, etc.) for editing the target file. In this tutorial we exploit the special case where `calibration.cal` already records the SWAT+ transformation, so every entry is set to `repl`. This instructs hydroMOPSO to overwrite the `chg_val` field with the candidate value exactly as it appears in the range definition, after which SWAT+ applies the appropriate `chg_typ` logic.

Because of this division of responsibilities, the bounds in `ParamRanges.txt` must be expressed in the same units that SWAT+ expects inside `calibration.cal`. For instance, the admissible range for `awc` is 10-300 because the model anticipates percentage changes, whereas `cn2` spans -20 to +20 because SWAT+ will add that offset to the original curve number.

Summary of change types

Parameter	SWAT+ chg_typ	Meaning	hydroMOPSO TypeChange	Meaning
perco	absval	Replaces the percolation coefficient in <code>hydrology.hyd</code> .	repl	Writes the value directly.
latq_co	absval	Replaces the lateral flow factor with no additional scaling.	repl	Writes the value directly.
alpha	absval	Replaces the baseflow alpha factor in <code>aquifer.aqu</code> .	repl	Writes the value directly.
cn2	abschg	Adds the supplied offset (-20..+20) to the curve number of each land use.	repl	Writes the value directly.
awc	pctchg	Applies the percentage change to soil layers 1-6 (100 = baseline).	repl	Writes the value directly.

Parameter	SWAT+ chg_typ	Meaning	hydroMOPSO TypeChange	Meaning
k	pctchg	Applies the percentage change to saturated hydraulic conductivity (layers 1-6).	repl	Writes the value directly.
flo_min	absval	Replaces the return-flow storage threshold in aquifer.aqu .	repl	Writes the value directly.
revap_min	absval	Replaces the revap threshold depth.	repl	Writes the value directly.
revap_co	absval	Replaces the revap coefficient.	repl	Writes the value directly.
deep_seep	absval	Replaces the deep percolation fraction (rchg_dp).	repl	Writes the value directly.

In short, hydroMOPSO offers several change operators, but SWAT+ already encapsulates the heavy lifting: `calibration.cal` knows which units, soil layers, HRUs or channels should receive each update. Leaning on that native logic is more efficient than replicating it on the optimiser side—hydroMOPSO simply refreshes the target values in `calibration.cal` and SWAT+ applies the correct transformation internally.

13 Appendix C: launcher for UNIX-like systems

This bash script only applies to UNIX-like systems (GNU/Linux and macOS). Windows users should instead run `rev60.5.7_64rel_win.exe` directly from the `TxtInOut` folder; the script below is unnecessary on that platform.

On UNIX-like systems remember to grant execute permissions to both the launcher and the platform-specific executable, e.g. `chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh` and `chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_linux` (or `_mac`). The wrapper detects the operating system at runtime before delegating to the appropriate binary:

- **GNU/Linux:** the script just calls `./rev60.5.7_64rel_linux`. You may execute that binary directly because no environment variables need to be set; we keep the wrapper for consistency with the other platforms.
- **macOS (Darwin):** the script first exports `DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.` so that the packaged Intel OpenMP runtime (`libiomp5.dylib`) located in the same `TxtInOut` directory is picked up before launching `rev60.5.7_64rel_mac`. Without this step the loader would report a missing library. This OpenMP runtime is required because SWAT+ is compiled with Intel Fortran/oneAPI; shipping the `.dylib` alongside the executable saves users from installing the full toolchain while still enabling multi-core sections of the code.

Other platforms receive a clear message instructing the user to obtain the matching executable.

```
#!/bin/bash

SCRIPT_DIR="$(cd "$(dirname "${BASH_SOURCE[0]}")" && pwd)"
cd "$SCRIPT_DIR"

OS_NAME="$(uname -s)"
ARCH_NAME="$(uname -m)"

if [[ "$OS_NAME" == "Linux" ]]; then
    ./rev60.5.7_64rel_linux
elif [[ "$OS_NAME" == "Darwin" && "$ARCH_NAME" == "arm64" ]]; then
    export DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.
    ./rev60.5.7_64rel_mac
else
    echo "Unsupported platform ${OS_NAME} ${ARCH_NAME}. Check or compile a matching SWAT+ executable."
    exit 1
fi
```